

Interdisciplinary teaching of ethics and translation to university students to provide social service to children with disabilities

Gerardo S. González Lara¹, Martha Catalina del Angel Castillo²

¹ Department of Humanistic Studies, School of Humanities and Education, Campus Monterrey, Tecnológico de Monterrey, Mexico

² Department of Modern Languages, School of Humanities and Education, Campus Monterrey, Tecnológico de Monterrey, Mexico

Email: gsgonzal@tec.mx, marthadelangel@tec.mx

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14060710>

Abstract

Despite the advance in technology for educational purposes, there is still a need for students to have a real-life experience outside the classroom. This leads professors to look for associations or companies that need the voluntary work of students from different fields. Designing a course with a social service component is a complex task because of the administrative processes within the institution and the academic training that professors need to acquire in order to design the content and activities of their courses. This paper describes the social service experience of two professors conducting interdisciplinary teaching of ethics and translation at a university located in northern Mexico. Thirteen students majoring in Music Production participated in a special semester called Semestre i (Semester i) designed by this university to engage students in Experiential Learning. In this project, students provided community service to a local association devoted to improving the quality of life of children with cerebral paralysis and their families through a comprehensive care model that promotes their maximum level of autonomy and inclusion in their environment. The association required the translation of an American manual of instruments used for various motor therapies to improve the speech, feeding, and sensitivity of children with disabilities. Therefore, professors taught students the principles of ethics and basic translation strategies through tailor-made activities so that they were able to provide this social service. The results showed that doctors, therapists, parents, and children were able to understand and use these instruments properly. Besides conducting social service, students committed themselves to the project cultivating empathy and embracing inclusion, and the Association and the University integrated relationship-building into more social service projects.

Keywords: Ethics, social service, language, interdisciplinarity, innovation.

1 Introduction

A traditional translation course allows students to practice translating material from various disciplines at their universities. These practices range from isolated sentences to books and magazines that pose challenges for this skill and with the help of the teacher, students can create different versions for the sake of a natural and faithful translation of the original text; very similar to what (Álvarez, 2012) calls a purely linguistic perspective; that is to say, the translation class was a way to learn the language through selections of texts with translations with comments on the lexicon, grammar or style. It was customary to read, translate, review, and correct the text in class, considering what was learned and the professor's feedback. Students tend to lose their motivation because this method becomes predictable and routinary to the point that if there happens to be confusion, it is corrected with no further consequences because the audience is represented only by the classmates and the teacher, in other words, the final version does not go outside the classroom.

Two university professors conducted interdisciplinary teaching: one professor of ethics and one professor of English-Spanish translation. The project took place at a university in northern Mexico with undergraduate students majoring in Music Production. Although following the interdisciplinary approach may have disadvantages such as integration confusion and time-consuming curriculum preparation, the advantages are enriching because it expands students' understanding and achievement between disciplines, enhancing communication skills (Jones, 2010).

Thirteen students majoring in Music Production participated in a special semester called Semestre i (Semester i) which was designed to give them the opportunity to have a real-life experience in their community so that their projects had a real 'customer'. For this university, Semestre i refers to a program in which undergraduate students strengthen and develop their skills through experiential learning experiences to face challenges together with companies and organizations throughout an academic semester (Tecnológico de Monterrey, 2017).

2 Experiential Learning Model

It is important to notice that Experiential Learning is a model that allows students to build their own perspectives on learning. In the words of (Chan, 2022): "A valuable experiential learning curriculum allows students to reflect, relearn, react, reinvent, reform and reapply their learning". Students who enrolled in this special semester participated as their interests were highly likely to align with the project's objectives which were meant to answer to the real-life needs of a community. Like most non-profit associations whose resources depend on donations and voluntary work, the ethical and translation skills students provided were welcome by the association.

The primary requirement to enrol in this project was for students to have already achieved a B2 level in accordance with the Common European Framework of Reference (Cambridge University & Assessment, 2023). It may appear odd that the measurement comes from a European, rather than an American institution. However, the Common European Framework is widely used because it covers other languages, making it easier for the university to contrast and compare scores across all their language classes, not just English. Nevertheless, it is also commonplace to write an exam in the United States or Canada and then convert the result to the Common European Framework. This way of measurement may also encourage applications in other languages, eventually.

The reason to require this level is rooted in the goal that students are advanced and independent enough to be able to understand the main ideas of the provided materials in the specific context they may find themselves in. It is important to remember that most students will need to step out of their comfort zone and delve into an area of knowledge to which they most likely have had little exposure.

Students provided community service to a local association that was founded for prevention, early diagnosis, and comprehensive care for people with cerebral paralysis and related conditions from early childhood in order to improve their opportunities for development and inclusion (Nuevo Amanecer, 2020). The association had just received an American manual with very detailed information about instruments that had been used successfully in the United States to improve the speaking, feeding, and sensitivity of children with disabilities. The personnel of the association were not able to use this information contained in the manual because nobody in their team could read this material written in English nor study the specification of use.

This fact reflects a reality in Mexico, but especially in the northern part of Mexico, where affordable and useful information is often available only in English. This comes from the fact that the USA is very prolific in teaching materials and updated information on the latest trends from different disciplines. The students in question may be very familiar with American documents, whereas the members of the association may not. Considering the topics inserted in Experiential Learning, this paper first presents a brief overview of the origin of social service in universities in the world and in Mexico. Then, it addresses the importance of teaching ethics and translation to carry out this social service with an association that seeks empathy and inclusion for its members. Subsequently, it describes how the classroom activities were linked with the needs of the community and finally, it includes the outcomes encountered by all the actors who lived this social and life-changing experience.

2.1 Social service in universities

In addition to teaching knowledge and values, it should be the duty of higher education institutions to promote through teaching the practice of those skills that prepare students to face various situations that require complex mental processes in their academic performance and later in the real world of building a career. According to Tecnológico de Monterrey Educational Model, the Social Service promotes the practice of volunteer work from students so that they fulfill their duties with the society as professionals and citizens (Tecnológico de Monterrey, 2016). This model was complemented with the approach of the Service Learning model (Aps) proposed by the Polytechnic University of Valencia (2020) in which they state that: "Service Learning is a teaching methodology that allows the training of students by putting the theoretical contents of the classroom at the service of society" in which, in addition to a methodology, this project requires a work protocol, in which the teachers involved, with the prior authorization of their Department Management, agree with the non-profit entities, public or private, with which they will carry out this didactic experience.

Therefore, in their general university education, students should acquire basic learning outcomes from scientific, technical, as well as ethical, and social points of view. It is important to note that in addition to these lessons, companies also demand academic skills like theoretical and practical training; instrumental abilities such as management skills; more than one language, and a good handle on computing; interpersonal skills like oral and written expression, leadership, teamwork, and cognitive skills like decision-making, critical thinking, daily reasoning, and creativity (García-Ruiz, 2023).

Social service is not something new but has been practiced in universities for a long and stable tradition and is linked to a specific branch of knowledge. An example of this social service practice is the study carried out with undergraduate students at the University of Michigan, USA with the theoretical course called Contemporary Political Issues where students from various disciplines carried out social service with community agencies, such as a nursing home, a crisis management center for women, an ecology development center, as well as counseling for primary and secondary students at risk of dropping out of their studies. The results showed that the students who participated in this project, with the social service component, agreed that volunteer work allowed them to commit themselves and feel useful to help their respective societies (Markus, Howard & King, 1993).

There are many initiatives developed to increase the relationship between universities and industries. In Mexico, the number of people interested in pursuing a major has increased because industrialization in the country has also increased significantly (Sagarra, Mar-Molinero, & Agasisti, 2017). Social service is carried out as part of the student's integral development at the undergraduate level by doing several activities with organizations and companies. Students are granted hours of social service which are mandatory and thus a requirement for graduation. The number of hours devoted to social service depends on each university.

For instance, a university located in the northern part of Mexico runs a program called Inglés Comunicativo para Normalistas in 2019 (Communicative English for Teacher-Training Students). The purpose of this program is to provide a space for social awareness to university students and to promote participatory and responsible citizenship. The students from different majors who participate in this project are required to have a C1 level of English according to the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (Cambridge University Press & Assessment, 2023) to be able to provide the opportunity for teacher-training students to develop communication skills by interacting in the English language for three hours on Saturday mornings for 15 weeks in the semester (Departamento de Lenguas Modernas, 2020).

2.2 The importance of teaching Ethics and English in universities

It is important to point out that the work of a professor is also to become an adviser who shows confidence and respect towards the different possibilities for professional development of every student so he/she can achieve integral professional training (Ayala, 2002). This ethical reflection is essential for educational institutions and for the current university student considering the immersion of technology and the scientific world in human actions, which tend to minimize the reflection of a humanistic nature; that is to say, ethics nowadays is very necessary but weak. That is why there must be instruments that are as clear as possible through which ethical values are understood and internalized throughout the student's university life (Etxeberría, 2002)

Thus, teaching ethics and translation to students at advanced levels of the English language is one key skill for cross-border life in northern Mexico. For instance, the university in question was modeled after MIT and has regular classes in English to both propel its local students to seek international exchanges and to enroll as many foreign students as possible to have an exchange in northern Mexico. Because of this, several classes already use textbooks in English, which are not merely translations of Spanish books but are actually textbooks used in other universities around the world. One can see that English continues to be the lingua franca as it is clearly defined by Seidlhofer (2005): "In recent years, the term 'English as a lingua franca' (ELF) has emerged as a way of referring to communication in English between speakers with different first languages."

The students who seek a translation course will most likely feel comfortable enough with the language to also take classes of their major exclusively in English and will then be accustomed to having reading material in English as part of their studies, which will be helpful as will be explained later. If this did not happen in the global world, students would not have access to updated information from different disciplines, nor would they be able to have contact with their international counterparts (Bobanovic & Grzanic, 2011) pointed out:

"In the corporate world, English is the most regularly used language and the knowledge of English has become one of the most important employability skills. Proper English does not only mean the ability to make grammatically correct sentences but also the other related skills for effective communication like presentation skills, convincing and negotiation skills, and interpersonal skills using English."

The American example, among others, has been pursued by universities in Mexico, especially those that aspire to have seamless communication and exchange of students with their American counterparts, even going so far as to arrange their yearly schedules to fit accordingly and improve the most important measures that rating lists look for in order to ultimately compete for the top spots with American universities. Social service may then just be another way in which Mexican universities choose to learn and even improve on the didactic designs as well as on academic and social results of other institutions from other parts of the world.

2.3 Linking the needs of the community through classroom activities

It should be noted that the objective of this university course is not at any time to train professional translators (written language) or professional interpreters (spoken language), but rather to confront learners with more complex cognitive processes in specific settings of their communities. Translation and interpretation techniques must be part of the fifth skill methodology (besides reading, listening, writing, and speaking) to master a foreign language and adapt the translated text to the level and specific needs of the students in which the teacher can communicate with the students in their native language. (Naimushin, 2002).

The students could also by inspiration from this activity ultimately pursue to become certified translators in their respective fields or other similar social services. This could especially be the case for those that seek to work for international companies or whose employer will depend on international clients or investors. Other fields that may have a special interest may be lawyers and doctors, as procedures in both countries have a very

specialized vocabulary where even translation tools may not be sufficient. Nevertheless, the teaching of translation and interpretation must be clearly distinguished from the traditional proper training of professional translators and interpreters.

Even more so, if students start off with an advanced enough level of English, it will help them understand and handle even technical terms of topic-specific complex texts. Furthermore, it would also come in handy when reading concrete and abstract topics when and if these terms are within their field of specialization. The users should be able to write clear and detailed texts on various topics, as well as to rebut an argument on general topics, indicating the pros and cons of the different points of view (Jiménez, 2011).

The time spent during the project should not be considered a limitation but rather an opportunity to put into practice what students have learned in the course by having real people with the need for a translation to access innovations. The field should be interesting to most students as it is quite a common service, such as dental health, applied to a specific group, children with cerebral paralysis. It is also encouraging that it may not be the primary service that the community thinks about when coming up with ways to help these children. Therefore, it is reasonable to assume that dental services may be easily overlooked in favor of more visible everyday activities.

This is an experience for one semester meeting three hours a week for fifteen weeks which is a useful point of reference to remind students of how much they will apply their knowledge to the project as it will most likely feel like an enormous amount of time. Students had two field trips to the local association: On the first visit to the facilities, both professors introduced students to the doctors, therapists, and some children, that is to say, the actual readers of their translation work. Students also had the opportunity to ask questions about the courses taught by the association, the profiles of the users, the limitations that children with cerebral paralysis encounter to be fed, swallowing their food, and the like. On this first immersion, students were able to see the needs of the association and how relevant this translation was for the health and welfare of children.

On their second visit, students participated in a social event organized by the association where children, personnel, and families from the association showed their academic work. This was an opportunity for students to feel part of the association which supports parents and their children to improve their quality of life together including volunteers and full-time personnel. After these visits, students were able to reinforce the need to assimilate the values of empathy and solidarity to perform this social service for a real social cause.

It was also refreshing to notice that there have been similar experiences in other fields. Although it should be noted that they have had limited exposure to actual social work. They have had great student outcomes though, so their example was considered a starting point for the project at hand. Even limited experience in a community service laboratory may change the way students' way of thinking regarding obligations and opportunities for social service and the people who need this service as well as a way of getting new relationships with the community to encourage volunteer work (Giles, Dwight & King, 1994).

This social service allowed big challenges in the content and didactics of ethics and translation courses. The activities for both courses were tailor-made. Some activities were designed to be done by students individually and some others to be done collaboratively. To teach ethical principles, the following is an example of one activity based on the classic short story called "The Pied Piper of Hamelin". After reading it, the student responded to questions to reflect on the ethical principles portrayed in the story. These are some of the open questions assigned for this activity and how one of the students replied:

Question: What initial values inspired the Pied Piper?

Student's response: Kindness, solidarity, empathy.

Question: Alluding to the Pied Piper of Hamelin as a metaphor, as a student majoring in Music Production, what values do you consider should always be practiced in your profession?

Students response: Those that the Pied Piper of Hamelin exhibited before being deceived as kindness and solidarity. Always seek that our work is to help others. In addition to this, always practice frankness to prevent us from being deceived, but also fidelity to our values so as not to forget them and then act wrongly.

Through this activity, one can see that students were able to identify values and how ethical and moral values are assimilated into their life and later as professionals. Empathy was one of the key values shown in the story so that they could put it into practice in their social service. Solidarity was another key value practiced in the social service for the association. A person that practices solidarity supports others in need. Philosophical ethics is inserted in the human condition and present in our daily life and impacts decision-making, reflecting a moral fact and awareness that should have been behind the person who made a certain decision. Thus, ethics is especially accessible to anyone because the language used is the so-called "ordinary language" spoken by ordinary citizens and not a formalized language such as logic or mathematics (Cortina & Connil, 2000).

As to the translation activities, the material in the manual was divided into six sections consisting of approximately 1,000 words in English depending on the number of images per page. Therefore, the class was divided into six teams so that students could work collaboratively on the section assigned by the professor. Previously, students were also trained with exercises about general topics in the classroom to later apply them to the project through translation strategies. For instance, the description of the products had to be precise for medical personnel and simple at the same time because parents and children would also read the material to select a product that matched their dental needs. One example of this type of adaptation was the following paragraph taken from the original version in the American Manual (Lowsky, 2018):

"ARK's DINO-BITE™. This "roarsome" T-Rex design is sure to be a hit with dinosaur fans. At 1.5 X 2.5" and just under 1/2" thick, this is a pretty 'beefy' chew pendant (and the longest-lasting necklace option for avid chewing). Great for chewing with the pre-molars and/or front teeth".

While the translated version was also targeted at any reader who wanted to select an instrument, shapes and measures were really important. For example, the dinosaur shape and the noises it makes made it attractive to children. The noises had to be onomatopoeic words and the measures had to be converted into centimeters. This was the translated version presented by one of the teams:

Dino-Bite de ARK™ [¡Este diseño de T-Rex hará rugir de alegría a los dino- fanáticos!] A los fanáticos de dinosaurios les encantará este espectacular [[Roartástico]] diseño de T-Rex. Con un tamaño de 3.8 x 6.3 cm y alrededor de 1.3 cm de espesor, este colgante es lo suficientemente "robusto" (Y la opción más duradera para uso constante). Ideal para morderse con premolares y/o dientes frontales.

In this translation, one can see that the adaptation from the source text to best suit the readers of this description of the instruments was essential. The adaptation has to do with cultural differences in the source language, English, and Spanish, as the target language. The culture of the United States and Mexico was reflected appropriately (Del Angel, 2019)

The students in question will no doubt have experience with online translator tools, as they are widely used by the public. Tools that translate individual words or a full text are commonly used, however, there are specialized tools that even professional translators use on a daily basis and that need some knowledge in order to get the most out of them. This is where the supervision of the professor has been key to have achieved a faithful and natural translation.

Technology has made various tools available to translators that allow them to carry out their work more efficiently and accurately. When translators work on a computer, it paves the way to have access to essential tools such as general, terminological, and encyclopedic dictionaries. This is called assisted translation which makes all the resources that may come in handy available automatically to translators (Oliver, 2016). There are cutting-edge technological tools to streamline the translation process from one language to another. However,

it is necessary to make a distinction between Computer-Assisted Translation (CAT) and Machine Translation (MT). TAO and TA are two processes that share a common objective: producing a text in one language that conveys the same message in another. Needless to say, they are two different processes in which human intervention makes a difference; that is, in the first, CAT, it is the translator who translates the text with the help of tools, and in the second, MT, there is no human intervention since the text is produced entirely by a machine. (Chueco, 2017).

The content of the class contained several strategies to be applied and students were not left alone in the process to test their newly acquired skills. Also, as a way to have a self-auditing process, students were asked to show their version to a native speaker of Spanish so that he/she could point out what was not clearly stated. This should be a humbling experience for the students as understanding the language does not automatically enable you to express it clearly and to the point.

As to the step-by-step evaluation of their translated version besides the feedback and changes suggested by the professor, students had to reflect on their own performance in order to ponder on their successes and mistakes and to also use their stronger areas towards a better performance on their weaker areas. These specific elements of self-understanding, such as goals, values, and obsessions promote action and self-regulation (Vallacher, Nowak, Froehlich & Rockloff, 2002).

Students also reflected on their collaborative work by considering not only their participation in the translation process itself, but also the organization of the team of students, the planning required to meet the deadlines agreed upon in the team, attending meetings to check the overall progress, and supporting their peers by identifying who's best suited for each part of the process with a self-assessment and co-assessment instrument designed by teachers specifically for this project. This is also an example of collaborative work in a didactic process: "Work, collaborative or otherwise, is best understood in terms of the context in which people are working, and its influence and constraints on structures and processes, performance and success." (Patel, Pettitt & Wilson, 2012).

Furthermore, the fact that the professor revised the final version and submitted it to the association validated the whole process and provided confidence that the work had been done accurately. Students reflected on the process about acknowledge and empathy with people with disabilities and the possibilities that the environment offers to support their opportunities and the student acts as a dynamic performer to achieve these efforts towards the community.

3 Conclusion

The purpose of this paper was to share how professors can prepare students to participate in social service through Experiential Learning. Although the exercises solved in the class were challenging for students, there was no real social cause behind them before this project came along. The outcomes that resulted from this project were very enriching for each of the actors participating in this project:

The professors were able to encounter the challenge of tailor-made design for this specific project and despite the possible disadvantages of interdisciplinary teaching stated by Jones, 2010 such as integration confusion, it was possible for the ethics professor and the translator professor to complement their content and activities because students needed to reflect on empathy and inclusion before they were able to visit the association or even read the manual.

The university in question, granted 100 hours of social work to students for supporting the association in this regard. It should be noted that students need a total of 480 hours of social service as a requirement for

graduation and that the students who were registered in this program were mainly freshmen, so it became very attractive to have 100 hours of social service during the first semester of their major.

The association because they received their Spanish translation of the 40-page American manual so that doctors were able to prescribe and describe thoroughly more than 50 varied types of ARK instruments available for different motor therapies for children with disabilities to improve their speech, feeding, and sensitivity. Both children and their families from the association were able to make a selection of the instrument(s) available to fulfil their needs.

University students, although some typical beginner mistakes were expected, such as coming up with a seemingly coherent but rather unnatural sentence in the final language, they were able to make a translation for a real need of an association and put into practice ethical principles in a real-life context to the point that they were no longer only plastic instruments to bite, but rather, instruments that saved and changed lives.

It may be argued that American and Mexican cultures are quite different. However, northern Mexico does have an ever-present dose of American culture within its borders. So, although the cultural differences have to be taken into account, we should not lose sight of the fact that they may be fewer than what other Latin American countries further south would have. This should be considered if and when this project is replicated somewhere else, maybe even between countries that don't even share a land border. In this sort of symbiosis, all involved participants certainly benefited from sharing knowledge, time, and skills but overall support for the other integrating relationship-building into more social service projects.

4 References

- Álvarez, S. (2012). La tecnología al servicio de la enseñanza de la traducción: diseño de un curso de traducción económica en modalidad mixta (presencial-virtual) y su experimentación en el aula. Tesis Doctoral. Universidad de Valladolid. Facultad de Traducción e Interpretación. Departamento de Lengua Española.
- Ayala, F. (2002). El profesor como asesor. Editorial Trillas.
- Bobanovic, Moira Kostic & Grzinic, Jasmina. (2011). "The importance of English language skills in the tourism sector: A comparative study of students/employees perceptions in Croatia." *Almatourism-Journal of Tourism, Culture and Territorial Development*, v 2, n4, p.10-23.
- Cambridge University Press & Asseement. (2023). International Language Standards. Available at <https://www.cambridgeenglish.org/exams-and-tests/cefr/>.
- Cortina, A., Connil, J., Coord. (2000). Diez palabras clave en la ética de las profesiones. Editorial Verbo Divino, Navarra, Spain.
- Chan, C. (2022). *Assessment for Experiential Learning*. [S.l.]: Routledge. ISBN 9780367863234. Available at <https://0-search-ebSCOhost-com.bibliotecails.tec.mx/login.aspx?direct=true&db=nlebk&AN=3358145&lang=es&site=eds-live&scope=site>
- Chueco, O. (2017). Análisis y comparativa de los sistemas educativos de diversas universidades en cuanto al uso y enseñanza de los programas de traducción asistida por ordenador.
- Del Angel, M. (2019). *Translation Strategies for English Language Learners*. Editorial digital del Tecnológico de Monterrey.
- Departamento de Lenguas Modernas. Inglés Comunicativo para Normalistas. Available at <https://sites.google.com/view/inscripcionss-mty/educaci%C3%B3n/66-ingl%C3%A9s-comunicativo-para-normalistas-2020>.
- Etxeberria, X. (2002). *Ética de las profesiones. Temas básicos*. Bilbao: Centro Universitario de la Compañía de Jesús. Desclée, Spain.
- García-Ruiz, R. (2006). Las competencias de los alumnos universitarios. *RIFOP: Revista interuniversitaria de formación del profesorado: continuación de la antigua Revista de Escuelas Normales*, 57 p. 253-270. Available at <https://dialnet.unirioja.es/servlet/articulo?codigo=2484287>.
- Giles, J., Dwight, E.; Eyler, J. (1994). The impact of a college community service laboratory on students' personal, social, and cognitive outcomes. *Journal of adolescence*, v17, n. 4, p. 327-339. Available at <https://digitalcommons.unomaha.edu/slcehighered/187>.
- Jiménez, C. (2011). El Marco Europeo Común de Referencia para las Lenguas y la comprensión teórica del conocimiento del lenguaje: exploración de una normatividad flexible para emprender acciones educativas. Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México.
- Jones, C. (2010). Interdisciplinary approach-advantages, disadvantages, and the future benefits of interdisciplinary studies. *Essai V7*, n1, p.75- 81. Available at <https://dc.cod.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1121&context=essai>
- Lowsky, D. (2018). ARK Therapeutic Services, Inc. Available at <https://www.arktherapeutic.com/>.
- Markus, G., Howard, J., King, D. (1993). Integrating Community Service and Classroom Instruction Enhances Learning: Results from an Experiment. *Educational Evaluation and Policy Analysis*, v15, n. 4, p. 410-19. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2307/1164538>
- Naimushin, B. (2002). Translation in Foreign Language Teaching: The Fifth Skill. *Modern English Teacher*, v11, n. 4, p. 46-49. Available at https://eprints.nbu.bg/id/eprint/1615/1/Naimushin_Translation_Fifth_Skill.pdf
- Nuevo Amanecer. (2020). Informe Anual 2019-2020. Available at <https://nuevoamanecer.edu.mx/nosotros.php#historia>.
- Oliver, A. (2016). *Herramientas tecnológicas para traductores*. Editorial UOC.

- Patel, H., Pettitt, M., Wilson, J. (2012). Factors of collaborative working: A framework for a collaboration model. *Applied Ergonomics*, v43, n1, p. 1-26. Available at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apergo.2011.04.009>
- Sagarra, M., Mar-Molinero, C., Agasisti, T. (2017). Exploring the efficiency of Mexican universities: Integrating Data Envelopment Analysis and Multidimensional Scaling. *Omega* v67, p. 123-133-
- Seidlhofer, B. (2002). English as a lingua franca. *ELT journal* v59, n4, p. 339-341.
- Vallacher, R., Nowak, A., Froehlich, M., Rockloff, M. (2002). The Dynamics of Self-Evaluation v6,n4, p.370-379, 2002. Available at <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/>.
- Tecnológico de Monterrey. (2016). Modelo Educativo Tec 21. p. 30.
- Tecnológico de Monterrey. (2017). ¿Qué es el semestre i? <https://semestrei.tec.mx/semestre-i>
- Universidad Politécnica de Valencia. (2020). Aprendizaje Servicio. <https://www.upv.es/contenidos/APS/>